

GRAPHNEYS – A GRAPH FRAMEWORK FOR REPRESENTING USER JOURNIES, IMPLEMENTATION & INFERENCE

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Abstract

Real-time analytics of online consumer interactions with brands compel highly scalable and robust implementations of data storage and processing. This is the key to interpret customer purchase journeys and make informed decisions for re-marketing, recommendation and customer retention strategies. Traditional methods for representing and storing the customer journey logs are dependent on High Performance Columnar Relational Databases. These state-of-the-art implementations are relatively easy and highly scalable. However, they rarely capture the explicit or implicit relationships between various entities within the data. These relationships between entities are crucial in understanding the wide array of patterns in their interactions. It is necessary to run computationally expensive jobs to capture such interactions and draw insights with representation of click-stream data sets using Relational Databases which is not scalable. The proposed methodology is to represent the click-stream datasets (entities and relationships) as heterogenous graphs. The nodes (entities) of these graphs can be of various types (users, pages, products, location etc.) and the edges of the graphs can be (visits [user, page], buys [user, product], from [user, location]) which captures the relationship between entities. A database of such massive graphs is called as Graph Database (GraphDB) This implementation facilitates the capture of interactions between entities through a better and intuitive representation. Neo4j which is an open source implementation of GraphDB is used to build the proposed heterogenous graphs out of terabytes of data. A comparative study is conducted to draft the advantages and the down-sides for the existing and proposed methodology. The experiments reveal that the proposed methodology outperforms the traditional database implementations in terms of space and time complexities while evaluating the results for semantically equivalent queries and analytical tasks. Another significant development observed due to the proposed implementation, is the ability to draw rapid inferences and insights from the interactions. These inferences are found to be desired in building highly scalable graphical models that can be used for predicting customer propensities to purchase, product recommendation, click prediction, and several other use-cases. This work also addresses how heterogenous graph implementations can be extended to other realworld data assets and discuss the ideal scenarios and limitations.

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1. Keywords

Click-stream data, Graph Databases, Graph Data Mining, Predictive Modelling, Recommender systems